

CITROSHEILD: Green Synthesis of a Silver Enhanced Bioenzyme Disinfectant from Citrus Peel Fermentation

P. Sai Sangeetha, T. Kirti Shervani, Mohammad Gulshan*

Institute of Pharmaceutical Technology, Sri Padmavati Mahila Visvavidyalayam (Women's University), Tirupati – 517502, Andhra Pradesh, India

ABSTRACT

Background: Chemical disinfectants such as Dettol, based on chloroxylenol, have been widely used for surface decontamination but are associated with environmental toxicity, aquatic ecotoxicity, and the promotion of antimicrobial resistance gene transfer. There is an urgent demand for naturally derived, biodegradable, and effective alternatives. **Objective:** The present study aimed to develop and evaluate a novel disinfectant spray—CITROSHEILD—by combining a citrus peel bioenzyme, prepared through accelerated fermentation using curd as a starter culture, with green-synthesized silver nanoparticles from silver nitrate (AgNO_3), and to compare its antimicrobial efficacy with that of Dettol (2% v/v) under identical conditions. **Methods:** Citrus fruit peels (300 g), jaggery (100 g), curd (50 mL), and potable water (1 L) were fermented for 30 days to produce the bioenzyme. Silver nitrate (AgNO_3) was added and the mixture heated at 60–70°C for 1 hour to synthesize silver nanoparticles via green reduction. Antimicrobial activity of CITROSHEILD and Dettol (both at 2% v/v) was evaluated by Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) determination using serial broth dilution against *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, and *Bacillus subtilis*. **Results:** The prepared CITROSHEILD spray showed MIC of 10^{-3} against *E. coli* (superior to Dettol at 10^{-2}), and equal MIC of 10^{-2} against both *S. aureus* and *Bacillus* spp. compared to Dettol. **Conclusion:** CITROSHEILD demonstrated broad-spectrum antimicrobial efficacy comparable to or better than Dettol, while being prepared entirely from biodegradable agricultural waste materials without synthetic chemicals. These findings support its potential as a sustainable, eco-friendly surface disinfectant for household and healthcare-adjacent applications.

Keywords: Bioenzyme; Green synthesis; Silver nanoparticles; Antimicrobial; Disinfectant; MIC

INTRODUCTION

Infectious diseases caused by pathogenic microorganisms represent one of the most persistent global public health challenges. Bacteria, fungi, and viruses can survive on surfaces for extended periods, making surface contamination a primary route of disease transmission in hospitals, households, schools, and public spaces. Chemical disinfectants such as Dettol, Savlon, and bleach-based products have been extensively deployed for microbial control. These products contain synthetic compounds including chloroxylenol, sodium hypochlorite, and benzalkonium chloride, which are effective against a broad range of pathogens. However, the massive consumption and relatively high chemical stability of chloroxylenol have resulted in documented ecotoxicological threats in receiving water bodies, with

detection in rivers at concentrations as high as 10.6 $\mu\text{g/L}$ causing endocrine disruption and embryonic mortality in aquatic organisms.¹ Furthermore, chloroxylenol at environmental concentrations promotes conjugative transfer of antibiotic resistance genes at rates 8 to 9-fold higher than controls, directly accelerating antimicrobial resistance—ranked among the top three major global public health threats by the World Health Organization, with an estimated 1.27 million deaths attributed to antimicrobial-resistant infections globally.² These concerns have created strong demand for disinfectants that are natural, safe, biodegradable, and equally effective. Bioenzymes, also termed eco-enzymes, are fermented organic liquids produced from fruit peels, natural sugars, and water. They are non-toxic, non-hazardous, non-corrosive, and biodegradable, and have demonstrated significant antibacterial and antioxidant properties.³

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Citrus peels, rich in flavonoids, phenolic acids, limonene, and citric acid, are particularly effective feedstocks for bioenzyme preparation due to their high bioactive compound content and support of microbial fermentation. In parallel, silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) have attracted exceptional scientific interest as broad-spectrum antimicrobial agents. Their antibacterial mechanisms include cell membrane disruption, free radical generation, thiol group interaction, prevention of DNA replication, and biofilm inhibition.⁴ Green synthesis, where plant extracts or fermented biological liquids act as natural reducing agents to convert silver nitrate (AgNO₃) into AgNPs, offers a cleaner and more sustainable alternative to toxic chemical synthesis methods. Phytochemicals in citrus peel extracts, especially citric acid, flavonoids, and polyphenols, are well-documented reducing and stabilizing agents for AgNP synthesis.⁵ The present study integrates bioenzyme preparation with green synthesis of AgNPs into a single novel formulation named CITROSHEILD. Citrus peels, jaggery, and curd were fermented for one month to prepare a bioenzyme, which then served as the green reducing medium for AgNP synthesis upon addition of AgNO₃ and heating. The resulting disinfectant spray was evaluated for antimicrobial efficacy through MIC determination using the serial dilution method against *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, and *Bacillus subtilis*, and directly compared with Dettol under identical conditions. This study contributes to the growing field of green nanotechnology and offers a cost-effective, natural, and eco-friendly alternative to synthetic chemical disinfectants.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

2.1 Bioenzymes as Natural Antimicrobials

Bioenzymes or eco-enzymes are organic solutions produced by microbial fermentation of biodegradable substrates including citrus peels, jaggery, and water. Dr. Rosukon Poompanvong of Thailand pioneered this technique in the 1970s, developing fermented eco-enzyme preparations as non-toxic alternatives to synthetic chemicals. Lakra et al. (2022) systematically evaluated physicochemical properties of bioenzymes from multiple fruit and vegetable peels, reporting amylase, protease, lipase, and

cellulase activities, and demonstrated applications in soil stabilization, water treatment, and household cleaning.³ Srimathi et al. (2020) established the one-month fermentation protocol as an effective shorter alternative to the conventional three-month process, confirming antimicrobial activity and cleaning efficacy of citrus bioenzymes. Sahu et al. (2024) demonstrated substantial antibacterial activity of orange peel bioenzyme against *E. coli*, *Mycobacterium smegmatis*, and *S. aureus*, with orange peel-derived bioenzymes showing highest antimicrobial potency.⁶ Benny et al. (2023) confirmed that citrus peel eco-enzyme produced during a ten-day fermentation with pH below 4.0 inhibited *S. aureus* with zones of inhibition of 31.85 to 34.41 mm.⁷ Mavani et al. (2020) reported MIC values of 50% for fruit peel eco-enzyme against *Enterococcus faecalis* with no significant difference in antimicrobial effect compared to 2.5% sodium hypochlorite, providing strong evidence that natural eco-enzymes can match the potency of established chemical disinfectants.⁸

2.2 Green Synthesis of Silver Nanoparticles Using Citrus Peel

Niluxsshun et al. (2021) synthesized AgNPs using peel extracts of three citrus species—*Citrus tangerina*, *Citrus sinensis*, and *Citrus limon*—confirming that phytochemicals act as effective reducing and stabilizing agents, producing nanoparticles 5 to 80 nm in size with broad-spectrum antibacterial activity against *E. coli* and *S. aureus*.⁵ Mogole et al. (2021) synthesized AgNPs from *Citrus sinensis* peel extract with surface plasmon resonance peaks at 400 to 450 nm, and TEM analysis confirming spherical AgNPs averaging 12 nm, with demonstrated activity against *S. aureus* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae*.⁹ Castañeda-Aude et al. (2023) produced ultra-small AgNPs averaging 2.42 nm from citrus peel residues with potent inhibitory activity against multidrug-resistant *S. aureus* at 15.625 to 62.50 ppm.¹⁰

2.3 Antimicrobial Mechanisms of Silver Nanoparticles

Dakal et al. (2016) published the foundational mechanistic review documenting that AgNPs exert antimicrobial effects via membrane disruption, reactive oxygen species (ROS) generation, protein synthesis interference, and prevention of DNA

replication. Because AgNPs attack bacteria through multiple simultaneous pathways, resistance development is significantly less likely than with single-mechanism antibiotics.⁴ Burduşel et al. (2018) confirmed MIC values of 0.625 mg/mL for AgNPs against *S. aureus*, and documented their broad-spectrum biocidal potential against bacteria, fungi, viruses, and *Mycobacterium*.

2.4 Research Gap

A systematic review of available literature reveals that while individual antimicrobial properties of citrus peel bioenzymes and green-synthesized AgNPs have been extensively documented, no published study has specifically investigated their combination into a single integrated disinfectant formulation using fermented citrus peel bioenzyme as both the antimicrobial base and the green reducing medium for AgNP synthesis from AgNO₃. No study has used curd as a starter culture in combination with citrus peels and jaggery for bioenzyme preparation, nor has any compared such a combined natural product with Dettol at identical 2% v/v concentration using the serial dilution MIC method against *E. coli*, *S. aureus*, and *Bacillus subtilis* simultaneously. The present study directly addresses this gap.

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1 Materials

Fresh citrus fruit peels (orange, lemon, or sweet lime) — 300 g; jaggery (organic, unrefined) — 100 g; curd (homemade, used as microbial starter culture) — 50 mL; potable water — 1 L; silver nitrate (AgNO₃, analytical grade); nutrient broth (NB); nutrient agar (NA); sterile distilled water. Bacterial strains used: *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, and *Bacillus subtilis* (standard laboratory strains). Instruments included: autoclave, hot air oven, laminar air flow cabinet, Bunsen burner, vortex mixer, incubator (37°C), glass tubes with caps, micropipettes, and parafilm.

3.2 Preparation of Citrus Peel Bioenzyme

Citrus fruit peels were washed thoroughly and cut into small pieces. They were weighed (300 g) and combined with jaggery (100 g), curd (50 mL), and potable water (1 L) in a clean, food-grade sealed container. The mixture was blended briefly and sealed airtight. The container was stored at room temperature (approximately 25–30°C) for 30 days, with the seal opened daily for the first week to release fermentation gases, and then sealed for the remaining period. After 30 days, the liquid was filtered through a double layer of muslin cloth to obtain a clear, mildly acidic brownish-yellow bioenzyme filtrate. This modified curd-based 30-day fermentation method is adapted from the standard 3:1:10 peel:jaggery:water protocol, wherein curd provides an active lactic acid bacterial consortium that accelerates acidification and enzyme production.

3.3 Green Synthesis of Silver Nanoparticles (AgNPs)

Silver nitrate solution was prepared at a concentration of 1 mM in sterile distilled water. The bioenzyme filtrate was used as the green reducing medium. AgNO₃ solution was added to the bioenzyme filtrate in a 1:4 ratio (v/v) and the mixture was heated at 60–70°C for 1 hour under constant stirring. The reaction was monitored visually: a characteristic color change from pale yellow to brownish-yellow indicated surface plasmon resonance (SPR), which is the standard visual confirmation of AgNP formation reported in published literature. The resulting solution containing bioenzyme-derived AgNPs (CITROSHEILD) was stored in amber glass bottles at 4°C until use. The underlying chemistry involves dissociation of AgNO₃ in the bioenzyme solution ($\text{AgNO}_3 \rightarrow \text{Ag}^+ + \text{NO}_3^-$), followed by green reduction of Ag⁺ to Ag⁰ by organic acids, flavonoids, and citric acid present in the bioenzyme ($\text{Ag}^+ + \text{e}^- \rightarrow \text{Ag}^0$), and subsequent clustering of silver atoms into nanoparticles ($n\text{Ag}^0 \rightarrow \text{AgNPs}$).

Figure 1. CITROSHEILD disinfectant spray — brownish-yellow bioenzyme with green-synthesized AgNPs in a 250 mL borosilicate beaker, foil-sealed after AgNO_3 reduction.

3.4 Preparation of 2% v/v Stock Solutions

Two percent (2% v/v) stock solutions were prepared for both the CITROSHEILD spray and Dettol by mixing 2 mL of each respective liquid with 98 mL of sterile distilled water. These stocks were used for all serial dilution experiments.

3.5 Preparation of Bacterial Inoculum

Pure cultures of *E. coli*, *S. aureus*, and *Bacillus subtilis* were maintained on nutrient agar slopes at 4°C. For each experiment, a single colony was inoculated into 10 mL of nutrient broth and incubated at 37°C for 18–24 hours to obtain an overnight culture. The turbidity of each culture was adjusted to match a 0.5 McFarland standard, corresponding to approximately 1.5×10^8 CFU/mL, using sterile NB as the diluent.

3.6 Serial Dilution and MIC Determination

Two independent sets (CITROSHEILD spray and Dettol) were prepared for each bacterium following the procedure below. The disinfectant concentration was held constant at 1.0% v/v throughout all tubes, while only the bacterial concentration was serially diluted via 1 mL transfers.

Step 1 — Tube preparation: Six sterile screw-cap glass tubes per set were labeled Tubes 1 through 6. Five millilitres of sterile NB was pipetted into each of the six tubes.

Step 2 — Disinfectant addition: Five millilitres of the 2% v/v disinfectant stock was added to each of Tubes 1 through 6, giving a final pre-inoculum volume of 10 mL per tube at 1.0% v/v disinfectant concentration throughout all tubes.

Step 3 — Serial bacterial transfer: One millilitre of the standardized bacterial inoculum was added to Tube 1 (total volume = 11 mL). Tube 1 was vortexed and 1 mL was transferred to Tube 2; Tube 2 was vortexed and 1 mL transferred to Tube 3, continuing through to Tube 6. One millilitre was discarded from Tube 6 to maintain uniform volumes. This produced bacterial dilutions of approximately 10^{-1} through 10^{-6} (exact dilution = $1/11^n$) as shown in Table 1.

Step 4 — Controls: A growth control (1 mL inoculum + 10 mL sterile NB, no disinfectant) and a sterility control (11 mL of 2% disinfectant stock, no inoculum) were prepared alongside each set.

Step 5 — Incubation and reading: All tubes were vortexed gently, sealed with parafilm, and incubated upright at 37°C for 24 ± 2 hours. After incubation, tubes were observed against a white background for turbidity. Turbid = bacterial growth (+); Clear = inhibition (-). MIC was defined as the lowest tube concentration showing no visible growth (first clear tube). Each experiment was performed in triplicate.

Table 1. Bacterial Serial Dilution Setup (Constant Disinfectant Concentration)

Tube	NB (mL)	2% Stock (mL)	Transfer (mL)	Total Vol. (mL)	Bacterial Dilution (Exact)	Dilution ($\approx 10^n$)
Tube 1	5	5	+ 1 mL inoculum	11	1/11	$\approx 10^{-1}$
Tube 2	5	5	1 mL from Tube 1	11	1/121	$\approx 10^{-2}$
Tube 3	5	5	1 mL from Tube 2	11	1/1,331	$\approx 10^{-3}$
Tube 4	5	5	1 mL from Tube 3	11	1/14,641	$\approx 10^{-4}$
Tube 5	5	5	1 mL from Tube 4	11	1/161,051	$\approx 10^{-5}$
Tube 6	5	5	1 mL from Tube 5	11	1/1,771,561	$\approx 10^{-6}$

Figure 2. Serial dilution tubes (Tubes 1–6) prepared with NB and 2% v/v disinfectant stock, before inoculation and incubation. Disinfectant concentration remains 1.0% v/v throughout all tubes. Bacterial concentration alone is serially reduced.

3.7 Aseptic Technique and Controls

All glassware and media were sterilized before use by autoclaving or hot air oven. A Bunsen burner was kept lit at all times during inoculation to create a sterile convection zone. Work surfaces were cleaned with 70% ethanol before and after use. A fresh sterile pipette was used for each dilution step. Positive controls (bacterial culture in NB without disinfectant) confirmed viable bacterial growth; negative controls (sterile NB only) confirmed media sterility.

RESULTS

4.1 Preparation of Bioenzyme and CITROSHEILD Spray

The 30-day curd-assisted fermentation produced a clear, mildly acidic (pH approximately 4.0–4.5)

brownish-yellow bioenzyme filtrate with a characteristic citrus aroma. Upon addition of AgNO_3 and heating at 60–70°C for 1 hour, the solution underwent a visible color change from pale yellow to brownish-yellow, indicating surface plasmon resonance characteristic of silver nanoparticle formation. No precipitation was observed, indicating stable colloidal nanoparticles within the bioenzyme matrix.

4.2 MIC Determination — Serial Broth Dilution

After 24 hours of incubation at 37°C, MIC values were recorded by visual turbidity assessment. The results are presented in Table 2. The disinfectant concentration was constant at 1.0% v/v across all tubes, and the MIC values refer to the bacterial dilution tube (10^{-1} through 10^{-6}) at which no visible growth was observed (first clear tube).

Table 2. MIC Values of CITROSHEILD Spray vs. Dettol Against Three Bacterial Species and Comparison of Outcomes

Bacterium	CITROSHEILD (AgNPs) MIC	Dettol MIC
Bacillus subtilis	10^{-2}	10^{-2}
Escherichia coli	10^{-3} *	10^{-2}
Staphylococcus aureus	10^{-2}	10^{-2}

Figure 3. Serial dilution tubes after 24-hour incubation at 37°C. Turbid tubes indicate bacterial growth; clear tubes indicate inhibition (MIC endpoint).

*** Lower MIC indicates higher antimicrobial potency. CITROSHEILD showed superior activity against E. coli compared to Dettol.**

The results demonstrate that CITROSHEILD exhibited broad-spectrum antimicrobial activity against all three tested organisms. It performed equivalently to Dettol against *Bacillus subtilis* (10^{-2}) and *Staphylococcus aureus* (10^{-2}), and showed

markedly superior inhibition against *Escherichia coli* (MIC 10^{-3} vs. 10^{-2} for Dettol), indicating one log-fold greater potency. No growth was observed in sterility controls, and vigorous growth was confirmed in positive controls, validating the experimental conditions.

Figure 4a. Nutrient agar plate showing growth of *Bacillus subtilis* (inoculated 3/3/26), used as the positive control organism.

Figure 4b. Nutrient agar plate showing growth of Escherichia coli (inoculated 3/3/26), used as the test organism for MIC determination.

Figure 4c. Nutrient agar plate showing growth of Staphylococcus aureus (inoculated 3/3/26), used as the test organism for MIC determination.

5. DISCUSSION

The findings of the present study confirm that CITROSHEILD, a novel disinfectant spray combining citrus peel bioenzyme with green-synthesized silver nanoparticles, possesses potent

broad-spectrum antimicrobial activity against all three selected test organisms. MIC values equivalent to Dettol against *B. subtilis* and *S. aureus*, and one log-fold superior activity against *E. coli*, strongly support the hypothesis that a naturally derived formulation can serve as an effective alternative to established

commercial disinfectants. The superior activity of CITROSHEILD against *E. coli* is particularly noteworthy. Gram-negative bacteria such as *E. coli* are generally regarded as more resistant to disinfectants due to their outer lipopolysaccharide membrane, which restricts penetration of antimicrobial agents. The better performance of the CITROSHEILD spray against *E. coli* compared to Dettol may be attributable to the multiple simultaneous antimicrobial mechanisms of AgNPs—membrane disruption, ROS generation, protein denaturation, and DNA damage—which are especially effective against gram-negative organisms at nanoscale contact.⁴ This multi-target mechanism also reduces the likelihood of resistance development. The equivalent performance against *B. subtilis* and *S. aureus* demonstrates that the formulation is equally effective against spore-forming and thick-walled gram-positive organisms. These results align well with published data: Wypij et al. (2021) reported MIC values of 8 µg/mL for biosynthesized AgNPs against *E. coli* and *P. aeruginosa*, and 128 µg/mL against *S. aureus*, consistent with gram-positive bacteria requiring higher AgNP concentrations for inhibition. Castañeda-Aude et al. (2023) confirmed potent inhibitory activity of citrus peel AgNPs against multidrug-resistant *S. aureus* at 15.625–62.50 ppm.¹⁰ The synergistic contribution of the bioenzyme matrix is also significant. Organic acids produced during citrus peel fermentation lower the pH of the solution, enhancing Ag⁺ ion release and activity. Enzymes such as proteases and cellulases present in the bioenzyme may degrade bacterial cell wall components independently, while flavonoids and phenols provide additional antimicrobial action. This combined effect—bioenzyme cleaning action plus multi-mechanism AgNP activity—likely accounts for the formulation's efficacy matching or exceeding that of chloroxylenol-based Dettol. From an environmental perspective, the current study demonstrates a complete absence of synthetic chemical inputs in the preparation. All raw materials—citrus peels, jaggery, curd, and AgNO₃—are either agricultural waste-derived or inorganic salts, and the overall formulation is biodegradable. This contrasts favorably with Dettol, whose active ingredient chloroxylenol has been linked to endocrine disruption in aquatic organisms and acceleration of antibiotic resistance gene transfer in the environment.¹ The study does

carry limitations that must be acknowledged. Only three bacterial species were evaluated, and assessment was restricted to visual turbidity after 24 hours. No colony count reduction, time-kill analysis, surface challenge test, cytotoxicity evaluation, or physicochemical characterization (UV-Vis, XRD, FTIR, TEM) of the AgNPs was performed in the present work. These represent important directions for future research, as complete characterization and in vivo safety assessment would be prerequisites for any regulatory or commercial application.

CONCLUSION

The present study demonstrates that CITROSHEILD—a silver-enhanced bioenzyme disinfectant prepared from citrus peel fermentation and green synthesis of AgNPs—possesses significant broad-spectrum antimicrobial activity against *Bacillus subtilis*, *Escherichia coli*, and *Staphylococcus aureus*. The formulation performed equally to Dettol against *B. subtilis* and *S. aureus*, and showed superior inhibition (one log-fold lower MIC) against *E. coli*. These results clearly support the primary objective of developing a natural disinfectant that can perform as effectively as a commercially established chemical disinfectant, while being prepared entirely from biodegradable, waste-derived, and low-cost materials without synthetic chemicals. The integration of citrus peel waste valorization, controlled lactic acid bacterial fermentation, and green nanotechnology in a single product represents a novel contribution to sustainable disinfectant development. CITROSHEILD holds promise for household, kitchen, bathroom, institutional, and healthcare-adjacent surface disinfection applications. Future work should encompass comprehensive AgNP characterization (UV-Vis SPR, XRD, TEM, FTIR, zeta potential), broader antimicrobial screening including *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae* and *Candida albicans*, shelf-life and stability studies, cytotoxicity evaluations, and surface efficacy testing under practical-use conditions to support translational development into a market-ready eco-friendly disinfectant.

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